

Why does it matter?

Hear it from our experts.

Vera Dimitrievska
Healthgroup

"Fertility represents a topic that targets biological families, straight couples, and many other categories of people. For example, B2-InF is fundamental for all those women who are very active in their careers and postpone becoming mothers later. I believe that the scientific knowledge generated by B2-InF will fill the gap in the grey literature around this issue."

Virginie Rozée
Ined

"The project proposes a legal, gender, and socio-cultural research perspective, which will allow a global and transversal analysis. This perspective is interesting and original as most studies on ART usually mobilize a single discipline. In addition, there is an undeniable pragmatic need for such a project as it aims to enlighten those working in the ART field, including policy makers, so that they can adapt their policies, medical offers, practices, communication and make them better fit with the young generation's expectations."

Jaime Onofre
The Walking Egg

"Over the last years, ART has interceded with much success, but also with many limitations in the current European socio-cultural context. Within this context, the assessment of knowledge, attitudes, and perceptions towards ART is of paramount importance. B2-InF recognizes this gap and is working to engage the public in the conversation. Our goal is to deliver clear and structured guidelines and recommendations to harmonize and direct future developments and provision services within the EU. Only this way ART can be a mainstay technology to support the Health and Wealth of European nations."

Anita Fincham
Fertility Europe

"With over 25 million people struggling to conceive in the EU, Fertility Europe advocates for fertility treatment accessible to all and fertility education as an essential life skill! Therefore, we support B2-InF's research on the perception of ART and information provided by the clinics in diverse European countries as we believe it to be a crucial step towards creating guidelines on reaching the young people with the right information at the right time! It can also help remove the stigma still associated with infertility and create friendly dialogue with young people and their educators."

Joke Struyf
University of Antwerp

"Me and my friends rarely thought about ART before we started a family: we had traditional ideas about how babies were conceived. Ten years on, many of our children would not have been born without ART. The way we perceived the hospitality of the fertility departments and the inclusivity of the available information had a major impact on our experiences. It is an honor to contribute to a project which aims to understand more about the expectations of ART and the way ART information is perceived, to improve the experiences people have with ART ultimately."

Kristien Hens
University of Antwerp

"Ten years ago, I started working as a postdoctoral researcher on the ethics of preimplantation genetic screening. I was fascinated by the many ethical and societal questions fertility treatment raises. I also enjoyed interviewing people undergoing fertility treatment and fertility doctors about their values and experiences. However, what was missing was the perspective of young people who have not yet used the services of fertility centers. Moreover, I also believed that there is a need to incorporate the perspectives of different genders."

Anna Dostalova & Michaela Novotna
Medistella

"We witnessed an increase in the number of people around the globe who are seeking advanced medical assistance to start their families. We hope that the B2-InF project will allow society to be better informed to make the best decisions possible in their journey towards building a family. Some countries that lack information on IVF will be able to implement adjustments in favor of their citizens and help spread awareness. The project aims to deliver potential patients the correct information they need saving them time and worry."

José Miguel Carrasco
Aplica Coop

"B2-InF matters to me because I strongly believe in giving voice to citizens and listening to those voices to act to improve societies. Reproduction and everything around it did not capture my attention until I met Francisco Güell by chance on a train and realized its significance as a public health issue, the lack of information about it, and the scarcity of scientific knowledge. Moreover, B2-inF matters to me because of the scientific and technical challenge that it presents. We have planned to carry out around 100 semi-structured interviews in 8 countries. Anyone who knows what implies the recruitment for and analysis of qualitative research will be aware of what it means!"